

ADHERENCE TO MANAGEMENT OF ALLERGIC RHINITIS AND REASONS FOR NON ADHERENCE AMONGST YOUNG EDUCATED INDIVIDUALS LIVING IN LAHORE

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Abstract

Background: Allergic rhinitis(AR) is a highly prevalent disease that has a profound effect on the functionality of the sufferer and can severely affect quality of life. It has far reaching consequences on health resources and the economy in general. Effective management is key to lessening the toll of the disease on the individual and the economy in general. In this article we look into adherence to the management protocol in young, educated individuals in Lahore and reasons for nonadherence.

Objective: To find out the perceived adherence to treatment of AR of the young educated population of Lahore and identify the reasons for nonadherence.

Methodology: A cross sectional study was conducted in Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan from December 2020 to January 2021. Questionnaires of the research topic were provided to individuals that met the inclusion criteria. The questionnaires were distributed both online and manually, with the majority of responses coming from individuals receiving the questionnaire online. Efforts were made to clarify what allergic rhinitis was to the possible respondents. One hundred and one questionnaires were filled and 15 were disregarded as they did not meet the inclusion criteria or were improperly filled. Data from 96 questionnaires was compiled, statistical data tabulated and finalized. Common trends and patterns were found and written.

Results: Only 23(24.0%) individuals reported to always take the appropriate dose of their AR medication at the right time. The major reasons for not adhering to appropriate doses at the right time included 58(60.4%) individuals stating that 'they tend to forget' to take their medication and 21(21.9%) individuals cited side effects of the medication as a reason for not adhering to their regimen. The majority of patients, 44(45.8%), reported to only taking medications when having symptoms and stopping when symptoms cease. 29(30.2%) individuals stated that they always use preventative measures. On asking the reasons for non-adherence (if present) to these preventative measures/ lifestyle changes advised, 23(24.0%) individuals identified job constraints as the reason for non-adherence whereas 24(25.0%) stated non availability of alternative means of transportation as the reason for non-adherence.

Conclusions: Adherence to medications and preventative measures in AR in young educated individuals of Lahore is generally low. Forgetfulness and side effects were the major reasons for non-adherence to medication. The main reasons for non-adherence to preventative measures were that job constraints and non-availability of alternative means of transportation made it difficult to avoid potential allergens.

Key words: allergy, allergic rhinitis, Lahore, adherence, non-adherence

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Allergic rhinitis (AR), often misconstrued as a trivial issue amongst the myriad of chronic diseases, is in actuality a 'chronic' nuisance for many sufferers. Although not immediately life threatening, the profound impact of this disease on quality of life cannot be understated. AR is highly prevalent with

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more 500 million affected globally¹ and is the most common chronic disease in children.² Even though many individuals do not seek medical advice for AR it accounted for 15.2 million visits to healthcare providers in 2003³ in the US. With advancements in medication protocols and better understanding of AR, management strategies have been refined such that they allow sufferers to lead relatively normal lives.

Allergic rhinitis, as the name implies has an allergic etiology. AR is an inflammatory disease of the upper airways related to an history of family atopy and is usually manifested in childhood or adolescence. AR is mediated by an Ig E related mechanism.⁴ AR is a chronic allergic disease and in this way is similar to asthma. Indeed, a significant number of sufferers of AR suffer from asthma.⁵ Note, AR is as debilitating as severe asthma.⁶

AR can affect an individual throughout the year or be seasonal⁷, the many symptoms of AR include sneezing, rhinorrhea, post nasal drip, irritation in the nose, blocked nose etc.⁸

There are various modalities for treating AR which include pharmacotherapy, immunotherapy and preventative measures.⁹ Recommendations support continuous rather than on demand treatment.^{10,11} Quality of life can be greatly impacted by allergic rhinitis. The symptoms (frequent sneezing, rhinorrhea, blocked nose etc.) can interfere with social interactions, work and adversely affect sleep.^{6,9,12,13} Not only does it affect the individual but it poses a great burden on resources in the form of direct economic cost, loss of man hours and poor work performance.^{14,15,16,17}

A key component in the effectiveness of any treatment protocol is how strictly the sufferers adhere to it. This is especially necessary in chronic diseases such as AR where the prolonged clinic course can be vexing and the monotonous application of medications can in itself be grievance and something that requires immense amounts of discipline. Indeed, even the most state of art treatments will fail if proper instructions regarding timing, administration and dosing are not followed. By questioning

sufferers of AR about the various factors that lead to their noncompliance, health professional will be able to more aptly gauge which areas need to be addressed in more detail during consultation and channel their efforts in a more focused manner to tackle these concerns in efforts to allay any possible fear or apprehensions that the patient may have and in turn possibly improve compliance to treatment. We therefore took keen interest in attaining further insight into how the compliance was amongst young educated individuals of Lahore and what the reasons were for non-compliance amongst this demographic. We focused on this demographic specifically as we came across no study focusing primarily on this cohort and present our findings in this article.

METHODOLOGY

It was a cross sectional study conducted in Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan from December 2020 to January 2021. Individuals with AR that were between the ages of 18 and 35 years of age and had completed their matriculation/equivalent or higher. Exclusion criteria included non consenting individuals, individuals below 18 years of age and above 35 years of age and individuals that haven't completed their matriculation/equivalent.

Questionnaires of the research topic were provided to individuals that met the inclusion criteria. The questionnaires were distributed both online and manually, with the majority of responses coming from individuals receiving the questionnaire online. Efforts were made to clarify what allergic rhinitis was to the possible respondents. 111 questionnaires were filled and 15 were disregarded as they did not meet the inclusion criteria or were improperly filled. Data from 96 questionnaires was compiled, statistical data tabulated and finalized. Common trends and patterns were found and written.

RESULTS

Of the initial 111 responses, 15 were disregarded due to the individuals not falling into the inclusion criteria or improper filling of the questionnaire.

As such, the sample population comprised 96 individuals with ages ranging from 19 years to 32 years with the majority (89-92.7%) falling in the 21 years to 28 years age range. 24(25.0%) individuals were suffering from other concomitant diseases, most of which were chronic in nature. Asthma was the most common concomitant disease and 10(10.4%) individuals suffered from diseases (specifically asthma, eczema and allergic conjunctivitis) that have allergic etiologies.

When inquired whether they experienced perennial or seasonal symptoms, 58(60.4%) answered that they experienced seasonal symptoms and 36(37.5%) answered that they experienced perennial symptoms with 2(2.1%) individuals failing to answer.

When given a list of possible symptoms to choose from 14(14.6%) individuals identified as having 1 of the symptoms, 12(12.5%) individuals had 2 symptoms, 24(25%) individuals had 3 symptoms, 29(30.2%) individuals had 4 symptoms, 8(8.3%) individuals had 5 symptoms and 9(9.4%) individuals had all 6 of the listed symptoms. 28(29.2%) individuals described their symptoms as mild. i.e. few symptoms that occur occasionally, 49(51.0%) individuals described their symptoms as moderate. i.e. few symptoms which are frequent or persistent and 19(19.8%) individuals described their symptoms as severe. i.e. multiple symptoms which are frequent or persistent.

On questioning the respondents on how the symptoms effected the quality of their life 39(40.6%) individuals stated that it adversely effects their work, 49(51.0%) individuals identified their symptoms as a reason for disturbed sleep, 35(36.5%) individuals stated that their symptoms interfere with social interactions. 17(17.8%) respondents felt that their symptoms did not affect their quality of life in the above-mentioned ways with 1(1.0%) respondent failing to answer.

Oral antiallergics were by far the most used medications with 70(72.9%) individuals stating that they used them, followed by nasal decongestants

used by 38(39.6%) individuals. Nasal steroids were used by 29(30.2%) individuals, Oral decongestants were used by 17(17.8%) individuals, 3(3.1%) individuals used oral steroid pills whilst 15(15.6%) individuals stated that they did not take any of the medications mentioned.

The majority of individuals had been prescribed their medications for more than 1 year with 39(40.6%) individuals falling in this category. At the other end of the spectrum 34(35.4%) individuals had been prescribed their medications for less than one month. 8(8.3%) Individuals had been prescribed their medications between 1 to 6 months prior and 6(6.3%) individuals had been prescribed their medications between 6 months and a year prior. 9(9.4%) individuals failed to respond. 19(19.8%) individuals believed that their medications conferred great benefit in relieving their symptoms, double this number 38(39.6%) of individuals stated that they did benefit from their medications whilst 34(35.4%) individuals stated that they somewhat benefit from their medications. Only 2(2.1%) individuals felt that they did not benefit from taking their medications. 3(3.1%) individuals failed to give a response. 42(43.8%) individuals reported to not have received any guidance for the application of nasal sprays and 52 (54.2%) stated that they did so. 2(2.1%) individuals failed to give a response.

When inquired on how often they experienced the taste of the nasal spray in their mouth on applying nasal sprays, few 15(15.6%) reported never experiencing the taste, with 34(35.4%) occasionally experiencing the taste and 40(41.7%) often experiencing the taste. 7 (7.3%) individuals failed to give an answer.

On asking how strictly they adhere to the timing and number of doses of the medication 23(24.0%) reported to always take the appropriate dose at the right time, 50(52.1%) stated that they occasionally forget to take a dose or occasionally take the dose at the wrong time whereas 18(18.8%) individuals reported that they often forget to take medications or often take doses at the wrong time. 5(5.2%) partici-

pants did not answer the question.

The respondents were asked about reasons for not adhering to medications appropriately. 5(5.2%) individuals cited cost as a reason, similarly 5(5.2%) individuals found the dosing protocols hard to follow. 58(60.4%) individuals stated that 'they tend to forget', 21(21.9%) individuals cited side effects of the medication as a reason for not adhering to their regimen. 11(11.5%) individuals found the drugs to be ineffective/ not curative, 4(4.2%) individuals stated that they were not able to understand the prescribing physician's instructions adequately.

On questioning how strictly did they adhere to the duration of the doses ('number of days you should take the medication for') of the prescribed medications, the majority 44(45.8%) reported to only taking medications when having symptoms and stopping when symptoms cease. 29 (30.2%) reported that they always took medications for the prescribed duration with 19(19.8%) individuals only taking medications when symptoms become severe. 27 (28.1%) individuals reported that they avoid exhaust fumes by decreasing travel by rickshaw or motor bike, when inquired on what lifestyle changes/preventative measures they followed. 29(30.2%) individuals reported that they limited outdoor activity during pollen season, 18(18.8%) individuals reported on using nasal douching, 48(50.0%) individuals reported that they used a facemask, 6(6.3%) individuals reported that they had stopped smoking whilst 18(18.8%) individuals stated that they did not use any of the mentioned preventative measures/lifestyle changes.

The majority of individuals had been advised preventative measures/lifestyle changes more than 1 year with ago 38(39.6%) individuals falling in this category. At the other end of the spectrum 11(11.5%) individuals had been advised preventative measures/lifestyle changes between 6 months and one year ago. 15(15.6%) Individuals had been advised preventative measures/lifestyle changes 1 to 6 months prior and 17(17.7%) individuals had been advised preventative measures/lifestyle changes less than a month

prior. 15(15.6%) individuals failed to respond.

When participants were asked to what extent do you feel using lifestyle changes/preventative measures helps with your allergic rhinitis 46(47.9%) individuals stated that they benefited from their lifestyle modification whilst 32(33.3%) individuals stated that they somewhat benefit. Only 6(6.3%) individuals felt that they did not benefit. While 4(4.2%) individuals stated that they greatly benefited from lifestyle change. 2(2.1%) individuals failed to give a response.

When participants were asked how is your adherence to the lifestyle changes/preventative measures advised? 29(30.2%) individuals stated that they always use preventative measures whilst 48(50.0%) individuals stated that they only use preventative measures when having symptoms, and stop when symptoms cease benefit. Only 12(12.5%) individuals only use preventative measures when symptoms become severe. 7(7.3%) individuals failed to give a response.

On asking what are the reasons for non-adherence (if present) to these preventative measures/lifestyle changes advised? 23(24.0%) individuals identified Job constraints as the reason for non-

Table 1: Reason for Non Adherence to Timing and Number of Doses of the Medication

Reason	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Cost of medication	5	5.2
Found dosing protocol hard to follow	5	5.2
Forgetfulness	58	60.4
Side effects of medications	21	21.9
Drugs are ineffective/not curative	11	11.5
Did not understand the prescriber's instructions adequately	4	4.2

adherence whereas 24(25.0%) stated non availability of alternative means of transportation as the reason for non-adherence. 13(13.5%) individuals were not able to understand the prescribing physician's instructions adequately 10(10.4%) individuals stated that the cost (of masks/nasal douches) was the cause of non-adherence while 8(8.3%) individuals stated that they find it difficult to stop

smoking. 35(36.5%) individuals failed to respond.

DISCUSSION

Compliance/adherence^{18,19} is a term that encompasses a compendium of factors^{20,21}, each contribu-

Table 2: Reason for Non Adherence to Preventative Measures/Lifestyle Changes

Reason	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Job constraints	23	24.0
Nonavailability of other means of transport	24	25.0
Did not understand the prescriber’s instructions adequately	13	13.5
Cost (of masks/ nasal douches	10	10.4
Finding it difficult to stop smoking	8	8.3

ting to a varying degree depending on the individual case. It is this case-to-case variability combined with the generally broad management protocol which includes not only medications but also lifestyle changes compounded with the chronic nature of allergic rhinitis that makes describing compliance with allergic rhinitis treatment and pin pointing reasons for noncompliance a particularly arduous task. Our article excludes any mention of immunotherapy despite it being a major and effective means of managing allergic rhinitis.^{22,23,24,25,26,27} This exclusion stems from the fact that Pakistan, as a whole, has very few facilities providing the treatment and it thus is not a norm to include it as part of a typical management protocol.

In our study we found that 22(22.9%) individuals were suffering from other concomitant diseases, most of which were chronic in nature of which asthma was the most common. Indeed the majority of allergic rhinitis patients suffer from respiratory problems.²⁸ Another study found that individuals with rhinitis were at a significant risk of asthma with a adjusted odd ratio of 3.2.²⁹ These findings are similar to our findings.

58(60.4%) answered that they experienced seasonal symptoms and 36(37.5%) answered that they experienced perennial symptoms of allergic rhinitis in our survey. Meltzer et al³⁰ found that 20% of adults and 21% children experienced allergic rhinitis

symptoms throughout the year, whilst 95% experienced symptoms in spring, 63% in summer and 74% experienced symptoms in fall. This study was conducted amongst US patients. We believe the dusty environment and poor air quality leads to a larger number of people experiencing perennial symptoms in Lahore.

Mild symptoms were experienced by 28(29.2%) individuals, 49(51.0%) individuals described their symptoms as moderate and 19(19.8%) individuals described their symptoms as severe. In another study³¹ it was found that 59% sufferers felt that their symptoms were moderately severe or severe. These findings further highlight the need to pay utmost attention in dealing with this issue. In a study conducted by Marple et al⁷ where 1 in 5 individuals felt that their symptoms weren’t taken seriously enough.

The overwhelming majority of individuals in our study felt that allergic rhinitis affected their quality of life in one way or the other with only 17.8% stating that their quality of life wasn’t affected. The literature is replete with studies emphasizing the effects of allergic rhinitis on quality of life. With effects documented on cognitive impairment, learning, decision making, psychosocial wellbeing, self-attractiveness and quality of life in general.^{13,32,33,34,35,36}

Bollinger et al³⁷ found that 39.1% were taking monotherapy whilst 11.0% were taking concurrent AR therapy. Of those taking monotherapy the most commonly prescribed were cough/cold medications (28.3%), intranasal corticosteroids (26.7%) and antihistamines (25.9%). Surprisingly 13.6% adults took oral steroids as monotherapy to treat their symptoms. Only 3(3.1%) individuals used oral steroid pills in our study and antihistamines were used by more than 70% individuals (note: this figure is the total value of individuals who use antihistamines as one of the medications in their protocol).

In our study, 77.1% of individuals complained of experiencing the taste of nasal sprays in their mouth with most stating that they often experienced the taste of sprays. One third of patients found the dripping of medication to be bothersome in another

study.³⁸ This is a highly concerning pattern as it implies that the patients were either not given adequate guidelines regarding nasal spray application or despite being given appropriate instructions were not following them properly.

Only 2 individuals in our study felt that their medication protocol conferred no benefit. The remaining felt that they experienced at least some benefit from using medications. In contrast a UK study found 54% of individuals felt that their symptoms were poorly controlled with a combined protocol of an intranasal corticosteroids and an antihistamine.³⁹ Another study found that only 3% felt that their intranasal corticosteroid conferred no benefit at all.³⁸

Non adherence to medical treatment is high in chronic conditions 30-60% and can be as high as 80% for preventative measures.⁴⁰ Sanchez et al also found adherence to pharmacotherapy was very low⁴¹ in AR.

35% individuals in another study indicated that they were non adherent for at least some time during the treatment, 38% stated that they discontinued treatment once they felt better^{42,43} the MASK Study also found that adherence to treatment in AR was low 44. 41% adults and 26% children reported taking medications year round in a study conducted by Meltzer,³⁰ this study also found that two thirds of individuals took their medication exactly as advised with a further 20% stating that they only took medications on the appearance of symptoms.

Our study found that only 23(24.0%) individuals reported to always take the appropriate dose at the right time and only 29(30.2%) reported that they always took medications for the prescribed duration which is in line with the findings of low adherence in other publications.

Numerous studies identify cost, forgetfulness, lack of efficacy and side effects and lack of efficacy as major reasons for non-adherence.^{45,46,47,48,49} In our study forgetfulness and side effects were identified as the most prevalent factors contributing to non-adherence. Complex treatment regimens and inade-

quate communication are also cited as factors for poor compliance.⁵⁰

The authors despite thorough review of available literature found very few articles talking about the reasons for non-adherence to preventative measures despite these guidelines being commonly advised. Allergen avoidance is the main basis of the preventative measures advised to manage allergic rhinitis. We were able to find one study that looked into pets as source of allergens and feasibility of implementing avoidance measures, this study found that only 4% of individuals followed medical recommendations regarding allergen avoidance with regards to pets.⁵¹

CONCLUSION

Adherence to medications and preventative measures in AR in young educated individuals of Lahore is generally low. Guidance regarding proper use of medications is inadequate. Forgetfulness and side effects were the major reason for non-adherence to medication. The main reasons for non-adherence to preventative measures are that job constraints and non-availability of alternative means of transportation make it difficult to avoid potential allergens.

Limitations of the Study

As we used convenience sampling to select the population group, this may slightly distort the results. Furthermore, as online questionnaires were a method employed by the authors it is possible that some of the questions weren't fully understood by the cohort despite efforts to ensure that the questionnaire was as easy to understand as possible. Since the authors did not have physical access to a large number of participants, it was not possible to confirm whether or not the individuals met the criteria to be considered sufferers of AR. As a result, some participants may consider themselves to have AR due to misdiagnosis by their physician, management by quacks etc. even though in reality they may not. One major limitation is that we did not use quantitative methods to quantify adherence and the responses were all subjective.

Recommendations

Studies focused on the adherence to different preventative measures should be performed as the region is vastly undiscovered. Strides should be taken to ensure that patients are given adequate instruction regarding proper administration technique; which will presumably lead to increased effectiveness of therapy. The importance of following medical instructions and risk factors vs benefits of all treatment modalities employed by health professionals should be properly conveyed to the patient thereby empowering patients to make an informed decision about the management of their disease.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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Contributions of the Authors

- Conception or design of the work- Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzaem Hussain
- Data collection- Dr Syed Ahmed Shahzain Hussain
- Data analysis and interpretation - Dr Syed Muzahir Hussain
- Drafting the article- Dr Syed Muzahir Hussain
- Critical revision of the article- Dr Muhammad Hasnain Haider
- Final approval of the version to be published - Dr Anas Zahid

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